

Effective Classification of Eye Disease Using Deep Learning Techniques

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Abstract— Sight and vision assist in connecting people to their surroundings. To continue interacting with the world, it is essential to keep your vision. Based on a report from the National Eye Institute states that 7.7 million Americans suffer from diabetic retinopathy. This may increase to 11.3 billion by 2030. There are many different types of retinal diseases. Some can be caused by genes inherited from your parents, while others can be caused by retinal damage that develops throughout your life. Early detection and diagnosis of retinal diseases are significant. Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) is a sophisticated non-invasive diagnostic scanning technology that shows the retina's cross section. In this work, we attempted to use deep learning algorithms to solve the problem of classifying various retinal diseases. Instead of handmade methods, deep learning models that automatically learn key features for specific tasks have progressively improved the performance of medical image analysis. This work mainly focuses on four categories namely CNV, DRUSEN, DME and NORMAL. In order to perform analysis, the publicly available retinal OCT images are collected and geometric transformation has been performed for the entire dataset. This resulted in the equalized compilation of a dataset which includes approximately 37,746 images. The dataset is fitted against three algorithms which have given us maximum accuracy namely VGG, 4-layer CNN(custom model), 5-layer CNN(custom model). Hyperparameter tuning has been performed to obtain improved accuracy. Parameters involved in tuning include epochs, optimizers, learning rate, etc. This research presents deep learning-models that can detect and diagnose eye disease.

Keywords— Eye disease Classification, Deep learning , CNN, Hyperparameter tuning ,Preprocessing

1. INTRODUCTION

The number of patients suffering from eye problems is predicted to increase and propel in the coming years as the population ages. Early detection and care of eye illnesses are the primary goals in this scenario to preserve eyesight and improve quality of life. Deep integration of deep learning in ophthalmology may be beneficial in this regard, as it has the ability to speed up the diagnosis process while reducing the number of human resources necessary. Deep learning excels at recognizing objects in visuals because it is implemented using three or more layers of artificial neural networks, each of which is responsible for extracting one or more image features. Optical Coherence is referred to as OCT. Tomography is a sophisticated scanning technique that uses optical reflection measurements to conduct noninvasive cross-sectional imaging of internal biological tissue structure that will enable ophthalmologists to see clearly into the rear of the eye and identify any early signs of retinal, macula, or optic nerve damage. The eyes are a crucial aspect of human life; everyone relies on their eyes to see and experience the world around them. Sight is one of the most important senses because it accounts for 80% of the information we get. By taking adequate care of our eyes, we can reduce our chances of going blind and losing our eyesight, while also keeping an eye out for any growing eye disorders such as DME and DRUSEN. Vision and eye health are two of the most important aspects of human life; they must be sustained in order for people to live. Eye diseases such as CNV, DRUSEN, AMD, and DME are primarily caused by retinal damage, and because the retina is damaged and discovered at late stages, there is almost no chance of reversing or curing the vision, which means that the patient will lose the ability to see partially or completely. Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) is a sophisticated scanning technology that uses optical reflections to provide non-invasive cross-sectional imaging of interior structures in biological tissues. Most people have vision problems at some point in their lives. The majority of people will experience visual issues at some point in their lives and they will go away on their own; however, other major eye problems require the intervention of specialist doctors.

In this research, the eye diseases considered are DME(Diabetic Macular Edema),DRUSEN, and Choroidal NeoVascularization(CNV).The sample images of these diseases are given in Fi2 1.1,1.2 and 1.3.

Fig 1.1 Diabetic Macular Edema

Fig 1.2 Drusen

Fig 1.3 Choroidal NeoVascularization

DME is due to the destruction of blood capillaries in the retina, a condition known as DME (Diabetic Macular Edema) can affect the eyes. Untreated DME will result in a build-up of liquid in the macula, which will then cause the retinal layer to swell and ultimately result in permanent blindness. DRUSEN is one of the initial symptoms of AMD pathology. Drusen, which are yellow deposits under the retina, are not symptoms of any eye illnesses, but their profusion can cause AMD and vision loss. Age-related Macular degeneration is a condition that damages the macula (a tiny area at the center of the retina), causes center blindness, and is currently incurable. In addition to affecting the patient's vision, this condition has been linked to heart illness and high blood pressure. CNV Vision loss is caused by the very prevalent disease known as choroidal neovascularization. includes the development of new blood vessels that enter the subretinal space or pigment epithelium from the choroid through a Bruch membrane tear. CNV can exacerbate any Bruch membrane damage.

2. RELATED WORK

This paper focuses on a four-class classification problem to automatically detect Choroidal Neovascularization (CNV), Diabetic Macular Edema (DME), DRUSEN, and NORMAL class in Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) images. The proposed deep learning classification model adopted two transfer-learning architecture and a categorical hinge loss as Support Vector Machine (SVM) instances to correctly classify retinal diseases in the retinal OCT dataset. The experiments follow a patient-level 10-fold cross-validation process using a retinal OCT image dataset. The proposed model is tested on the benchmark data with exactly 84495 grey-scale images labelled into 4 classes. The experimental evaluation shows that the proposed model outperforms the conventional deep learning state of the art reported on the OCT dataset with an overall accuracy of 98% for the Xception model and 93% for The inception V3 model.[1]There are about 12 million people in India compared to 39 million people who are blind in the world. Sadly, 85% of these cases are curable. It has been established that the most common underlying causes of blindness are due to diabetic retinopathy, glaucoma, and cataracts. Therefore, in this article, he proposes an automatic or self-diagnostic procedure that uses deep learning models to detect all three diseases within 1 minute with a high prediction rate. Various classification systems have been developed over the years, all of which have improved significantly over the last decade. Logistic regression, SVM (support vector machines), decision trees, KNN (K – Nearest Neighbors), random forests, and backpropagation are just a few of the many classification models available. In this study, we propose a DCNN-based expert system that resembles the human brain with inputs, neurons, hidden layers, and outputs to diagnose three diseases via an online platform. In this study, fundus images of healthy and affected patients are acquired under good lighting conditions to reveal hidden features. The fundus image is then subjected to image processing techniques

such as grayscale, resizing, and power conversion. Finally, a deep CNN is generated using the hidden layer, 16 input neurons and 2 normal or affected output neurons. Detection accuracy was 91% for DR, 90% for cataract, and 86% for images affected by glaucoma. A user-friendly and interpretable online graphical user interface (GUI) was developed with the system.[2]

Medical image classification plays an important role in disease monitoring and detection. This paper describes a deep learning approach to discriminate between images obtained by optical coherence tomography techniques of normal eyes and three eye diseases called diabetic macular edema (DME), choroidal neovascularization (CNV) and DURSEN. I will explain. This section explains. I'll show you how. To achieve this goal, the image goes through a localization process. The extracted patches are processed as sequences and a recurrent neural network is applied to classify the images. Four pre-trained models including VGG16, ResNet152V2, NasnetMobile, Densnet169 and Vision Transformer are also implemented and compared. Based on the results, the test accuracy of the proposed model reached 99.38%, which is higher than other models.[3] Medical image classification plays a key role in disease monitoring and detection. This paper presents deep learning methods to distinguish images captured by optical coherence tomography of a normal eye and three eye-related diseases, namely diabetic macular edema (DME), choroidal neovascularization (CNV), and DURSEN. To reach this goal, the images undergo a process of localization; then the extracted patches are processed as sequences and recurrent neural networks are applied to classify the images. Also, four pre-trained models including VGG16, ResNet152V2, NasnetMobile and Densnet169 and the vision converter model are implemented and compared. Based on the results, the proposed model achieved a test accuracy of 99.38%, which is higher than other models.[4] The OCT images of patients are divided into four categories in this paper using deep learning models: Choroidal neovascularization (CNV), Diabetic macular edema (DME), Drusen, and Normal. There are two different models suggested. In one, three binary Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) classifiers are used, while in the other, four binary CNN classifiers are used. With 0.987 accuracy, 0.987 sensitivity, and 0.996 specificity, the proposed model using VGG16 for CNV vs. other classes, VGG16 for DME vs. other classes, VGG19 for Drusen vs. other classes, and InceptionV3 for Normal vs. other classes performs the best among them. The accuracy of the binary classifier for the Normal class is 0.999.[5] The fusion of two previously trained deep learning networks is suggested as a way to enhance automated classification and detection of macular diseases using retinal Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) images. To create the long feature vector of the fused network, the extracted feature vectors from each pre-trained deep learning model are concatenated. The experimental results showed that, on the same dataset, combining two Deep Convolution Neural Networks (DCNN) improves classification accuracy compared to doing so separately. The large-scale screening and the recommendation of a diagnosis to an ophthalmologist can be helped by the automated retinal OCT image classification.[6] Ophthalmologists can diagnose eye diseases with the help of automated image processing provided by digital fundus cameras. Older people's declining vision and age-related eye disorders are most frequently caused by cataracts, glaucoma, and other retinal diseases. The classification of different eye disorders using a computer-based intelligent approach is very helpful for both disease detection and disease prevention. This study describes a categorization method based on deep learning for four different types of digital retinal images (DRI). A Kaggle database of 602 DRI weighing 1.67 GB is used to test the invariant of the Inception v4 model. The results are very encouraging, and we achieve an accuracy rate of 96%.[7]

In this study, we classify four different eye movements using electrooculogram (EOG) signals obtained from four sensors placed on the muscles that control eye movement in both the horizontal and vertical directions. The output of the classifier is used to operate a wheelchair or any other device created to assist ALS patients in going about their daily lives. In this study, the EOG signals are fed directly into two deep neural networks using, respectively, the long-short term memory (LSTM) and the convolutional neural network (CNN). This differs from traditional classification techniques, which first extract features from the EOG signals before using them with a trained classifier. According to the results, the CNN network and

LSTM network both classify eye movements with an accuracy of 90.3%. [8] The proposed method is divided into two steps. Pretreatments were conducted in the first stage to eliminate retinal pictures from various data sets and standardize them in size. Convolutional Neural Network, a deep learning method, was used to classify data in the second stage, with 98.5% success. The main distinction between this study and others is that instead of manually building the feature set as in previous approaches, the deep learning network automatically constructs itself in a very short period by employing the CPU and GPU during the training phase. [9] The fundamental purpose is to gather common characteristics from any creature, object, occurrence, or event in the real or abstract universe. Convolutional Neural Networks are Artificial Neural Networks that are utilized in intelligent pattern classification, Machine Learning, and Data Mining. These algorithms were also employed in medicine and ophthalmology to detect disorders in the human body. The K-Fold Cross Validation test is used to validate a revolutionary intelligent pattern categorization method based on a Convolutional Neural network. There are two types of retinography images provided: Glaucoma and Diabetic Retinopathy. The percentage of accuracy was 99.89%. Numerical measures such as Accuracy, Recall, Specificity Precision, and F 1 score with values close to one, as well as ROC curves, support the suggested classifier's appropriate performance. [10] A robust deep learning model is suggested for the identification of glaucoma. This detection process comprises three stages: gathering images, segmenting them, and performing the detection. Initially, necessary images are sourced from established benchmarks. Next, these collected images undergo segmentation of the optic cup and disc. This segmentation utilizes the Trans-MobileUnet with a novel loss function (TMUnet-NL) to achieve optimal results. The image, segmented with minimal loss, is input into the Attention-based Dilated Hybrid Network (ADHNet) for final detection. This solution effectively classifies eye diseases by leveraging the advantages of both Dilated and attention-based models, specifically VGG16 and DTCN. Within the ADHNet framework, the VGG16 network extracts features from the cup, disc, and raw images. These extracted features from the cup, disc, and overall images are then combined and provided to the Deep Temporal Convolution Network (DTCN) for glaucoma detection. Compared to traditional methods, this proposed approach achieves an impressive accuracy rate of 94%. Early and accurate intervention for eye diseases can help mitigate the risk of vision loss. The importance of eye disease detection mainly hinges on early identification to improve treatment results and provide more effective strategies for eye health management. Implementing a deep learning model can enhance the segmentation and classification of eye diseases, supporting clinical experts in their decision-making process. Regular eye checks performed by clinical professionals contribute to improved vision and enhance the quality of everyday life. [11] The retina plays an essential role in the eye by capturing visual information, highlighting the necessity of maintaining retinal health for clear vision. A range of eye disorders, including age-related macular degeneration, diabetic retinopathy, and glaucoma, can significantly affect vision and potentially result in blindness if not recognized and treated promptly. Consequently, automated systems that utilize machine learning and computer vision methods have demonstrated potential for the early identification and management of these conditions, thereby lowering the likelihood of vision loss. In this regard, we have developed a comprehensive dataset to support the creation and assessment of machine learning models aimed at detecting eye diseases. This dataset was gathered over an eight-month period from Anawara Hamida Eye Hospital & B.N.S.B. Zahurul Haque Eye Hospital using a Color Fundus Photography machine. It consists of two types of data: color fundus photographs and images of the anterior segment. The color fundus photographs are divided into nine categories: Diabetic Retinopathy, Glaucoma, Macular Scar, Optic Disc Edema, Central Serous Chorioretinopathy (CSCR), Retinal Detachment, Retinitis Pigmentosa, Myopia, and Healthy, while the anterior segment images are classified into one category: Pterygium. This dataset includes a total of 5,335 primary images. By offering a rich and varied collection of color fundus photographs, this dataset proves to be a significant resource for researchers and clinicians in ophthalmology, facilitating the automated identification of nine distinct categories of eye diseases. [12]

3. METHODOLOGY

The system design diagram is given in Fig 2. The system design involves collecting the dataset which contains three different eye modalities also called as diseases created using image assets. The data is anonymous and contains no private information. The dataset contains 37,746 images with folders categorized into train, test and val. The pre-processing techniques includes image resizing which includes changing the size of the image from one to another, geometric transformation which means to give an entity the desired position, orientation, or shape starting from the current position, orientation, or shape, geometric transformations are required. Scaling, rotation, translation, and shear are the fundamental transformations and noise reduction which means changing the original image with a mask that is like a low-pass filter or some sort of smoothing operation. The goal at the end is to estimate the original picture by decreasing noise from a noisy version of the image. The user inputs a test image for testing and the model works as the from the following algorithms- VGG, 4 layer CNN and 5 layer CNN. The VGG consists of convolution layer, pooling layer, activation layer and fully connected layer. The 4 layer and 5 layer CNN consists of extra 4 and 5 layer convolution layers which helps in improvising the accuracy.

Fig. 2 System Design

Instead of having a large number of hyperparameters, the VGG-19 is a CNN-based model that uses 3 3 filters with a single stride and consistently uses the same padding and maxpooling layers of 2 2 filters with a stride of 2. The convolution and maxpooling layers are arranged similarly in the architecture. The model contains two FC levels. This VGG-19 network is a large network with about 138 million trainable

parameters. In applications for object recognition and picture classification, the convolutional neural network performs exceptionally well. One machine learning technique for creating Multilayer Perceptron (MLPs) that process two-dimensional input is CNNs (convolutional neural networks). CNNs are a sort of deep neural network because they have various methods for fusing picture data together in a network. The Adam optimizer and a binary cross-entropy loss function are set up in the model. The sigmoid activation function is also employed. Every experiment was run through Google Colab. The hyperparameter tuning of the parameters like learning rate, epoch, steps per epoch, number of layers, order of layers, types of layers, number of nodes in each layer, regularization. The learning rate means a hyper-parameter used to control how quickly an algorithm updates or learns the values of a parameter estimate is known as the learning rate and is represented by the symbol. In other words, our neural network's weights with respect to the loss gradient are controlled by the learning rate. An epoch is the total number of iterations required to train the machine learning model using all of the training data at once. It is measured in cycles. The number of trips a training dataset makes around an algorithm is another way to define an epoch. Regularisation is a collective term for a variety of methods used to reduce a neural network model's complexity during training and avoid overfitting. L1, L2, and dropout are three highly well-liked and effective regularisation methods. The final result comes in a text format stating the accuracy of the image uploaded for testing compared with the trained data from the dataset. And the accurate result is displayed to the end user such as doctor, medical analyst and patients.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A.Dataset

The dataset is divided into the following 3 folders: train, test, and valuation, with a subfolder for each type of picture (NORMAL, CNV, DME, and DRUSEN). There are 4 categories (NORMAL, CNV, DME, and DRUSEN) and 84,495 X-Ray pictures (JPEG).

Images are categorized into 4 directories: CNV, DME, DRUSEN, and NORMAL and labeled as (disease)-(randomized patient ID)-(image number by this patient).

From retrospective cohorts of adult patients at the Shiley Eye Institute of the University of California San Diego, the California Retinal Research Foundation, Medical Centre Ophthalmology Associates, the Shanghai First People's Hospital, and the Beijing Tongren Eye Centre between July 1, 2013, and March 1, 2017, optical coherence tomography (OCT) images (Spectralis OCT, Heidelberg Engineering, Germany) were chosen.

B.Preprocessing

For the above dataset, we have performed geometric transformation. Geometric transformation changes the positions of pixels in a picture while leaving the colors unaltered. This technique helps to resize all the images in the dataset to be of the same dimensions. The preprocessed image is given in Fig.3 Thus, this improves the accuracy of the algorithms.

. Fig 3.Preprocessed image

C.Algorithms

We have tried various algorithms such as VGG, Xception, Resnet and modified custom models. Of these, We would like to explain the algorithms which have given us maximum accuracy. The parameters such as Epochs, Steps per epochs, optimizer, learning rate are modified to obtain maximum accuracy. We have involved Grid Search CV to perform the hyper parameter tuning.

1. VGG

It is a typical deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) design with several layers, and the abbreviation VGG stands for Visual Geometry Group. With VGG-16, there are 16 convolutional layers, the term "deep" refers to the number of layers. Innovative object identification models are built using the VGG architecture. The VGGNet, created as a deep neural network, outperforms benchmarks on a variety of tasks and datasets outside of ImageNet. It is also remains one of the most often used image recognition architectures today. Here, we have included the architectural diagram of the algorithm that has been generated by the model.VGG architecture in given in Fig .4

Fig 34 Architecture of VGG

2. Four-Layered CNN (Custom model)

A CNN is a particular type of network architecture for deep learning algorithms that is utilized for tasks like image recognition and pixel data processing. The structure of a CNN is comparable to the connection structure of the human brain. A convolutional layer, a pooling layer, and a fully connected (FC) layer make up a deep-learning CNN. The first layer is the convolutional layer, while the final layer is the FC layer. Here in this model, we have modified the layers of CNN. Four sets of convolution layers followed by the pooling layer are introduced. The architecture of the model is as follows. Architecture of 4 layered CNN is given in Fig 5

Fig 5 Architecture of 4-Layered CNN

3. Five-Layered CNN (Custom model)

A deep-learning CNN is composed of three layers: a convolutional layer, a pooling layer, and a fully connected (FC) layer. Convolutional layer is the first layer, while the FC layer is the last layer. Here in this

model, we have modified the layers of CNN. Five sets of convolution layers followed by the pooling layer are introduced. The architecture of the model is given in Fig 6.

Fig 6 Architecture of 5-Layered CNN

The table.1 shows the major findings obtained by hyperparameter tuning. The various parameters such as epochs, learning rate, optimizer etc has been altered and modified to increase the accuracy of the models

Algorithm	Epochs/Steps per epoch	Train Accuracy	Test Accuracy
VGG	1/100	87.50	88.53
	9/100	87.50	91.21
VGG with finetuning	1/100	96.88	94.83
	9/100	96.88	98.03
4 Layer CNN	5/100	66.89	85.1
4-layer CNN with finetuning	10/100	81.97	94.32
5 Layer CNN	1/100	39.42	73.76
	5/100	77.02	90.8
5 Layer CNN with finetuning	10/100	90.56	97.73

Table 1 : Performance Comparison

The above table shows the major findings obtained by hyperparameter tuning. The various parameters such as epochs, learning rate, optimizer etc has been altered and modified to increase the accuracy of the models

Fig 7 Accuracy of VGG plot

5. CONCLUSIONS

The main goal of this project is to develop a deep learning model that can predict and classify the OCT images with maximum accuracy. With the help of this project, the medical professionals and individuals are able to easily classify the retinal disease as the model has been trained against thousands of images. Thus, it reduces human assumptions of diseases which may lead to wrong treatments. This application is useful and will be a go-to for retinal treating centers. This application will be available throughout the day, so we can get any information at any time. It reduces the struggle of medical practitioners and patients by reducing the time taken and cost of the process. Many concerns were taken to obtain maximum accuracy as the project deals with medical image classification. A minor deviation may lead to serious health related issues. This paper proposes deep learning methods to classify OCT images into four classes CNV, DME, DRUSEN, and NORMAL using the chosen models. The maximum accuracy obtained for VGG is 98.03% after finetuning the parameters such as epochs, learning rate, optimizer etc. The maximum accuracy obtained for 5 layer is 97.73% after finetuning the parameters. The maximum accuracy obtained for 4 layer is 94.32% after finetuning the parameters. Hence VGG which contains the maximum accuracy is considered as the end result and final model

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